

Deuteration and Macromolecular Crystallisation (DEMAX) Certificate of Analysis for Chemical Deuteration

Proposal ID	979E6CS6
Principle Investigator	Vinardas Kelpsas
Structure/Description	<p>Sodium pyruvate-<i>d</i>₃</p>
Code	AEL02117
Producer	Anna Leung
Mass	10.0 g
% Deuteration	90.0% (+/- 2%) by mass spec
Analyses	<input type="checkbox"/> ¹ H NMR spectrum <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ¹³ C NMR spectrum <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mass spectrum <input type="checkbox"/> TLC plate <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____

Figure 1. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of sodium pyruvate- d_3 (AEL02117) in D_2O with 1% (w/w) 3-(trimethylsilyl)-1-propanesulfonic acid, sodium salt (DSS) (reference) with the expanded region showing the CD₃ signal of sodium pyruvate- d_3 .

Figure 2. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of D_2O with 1% (w/w) 3-(trimethylsilyl)-1-propanesulfonic acid, sodium salt (DSS).

Figure 3. ESI-MS of sodium pyruvate- d_3 (AEL02117).

Calculation of % Deuteration from MS Isotope Distribution									
Note: Always label the lowest m/z peak as Peak No. 1 & increment each subsequent peak by 1 m/z unit									
Parent Ion Peak No.	Theoretical % D for Peak	Peak Area	Corrected Peak Area	Contribution of Peak to Overall % D	^{13}C Isotopic Distribution from ChemDraw:		Theoretical % D for Peak	Corrected Peak Area	Amount (%) of compound at Theoretical % D
1	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0000E+00	0,0	^{13}C # 2	3,2	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
2	33,3	7,5358E+05	7,5358E+05	1,0	^{13}C # 3	0	33,3	7,5358E+05	3,0
3	66,7	6,0953E+06	6,0712E+06	16,2	Total Corrected Area of all Isotopic Peaks		66,7	6,0712E+06	24,3
4	100,0	1,8360E+07	1,8165E+07	72,7	Average % Deuteration of Molecule		100,0	1,8165E+07	72,7
5			0,0000E+00	0,0	89,9		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
6			0,0000E+00	0,0	Error = +/- 2 %		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
7			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
8			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
9			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
10			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
11			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
12			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
13			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
14			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
15			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
16			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
17			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
18			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
19			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
20			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
21			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
22			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
23			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
24			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
25			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
26			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
27			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
28			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
29			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
30			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0

Figure 4. Calculation of deuteration percentage of sodium pyruvate- d_3 (AEL02117) based on ESI-MS.